
Research

Comprehensive evaluation of different powertrain vehicles based on the EWM-TOPSIS-AISM Method: a case of China

Zixiang Bian¹, Zikui Bian^{2*}, Xunping Lei³, Mohammad Kamrul Hasan³, Wei Li⁴

¹School of Communications and Transportation, Shijiazhuang Tiedao University, China

²College of Science, Hebei University of Technology, China

³School of Business Administration, Tongling University, China

⁴China Railway Beijing Group Co., LTD, China

Abstract: Since the end of 2023, several European and American car companies have begun to slow down or even abandon the process of promoting electric vehicles. How to deduce the reasonable timing for the promotion of electric vehicles based on the actual situation of each country is an important issue in the promotion of electric vehicles in each country. This paper, taking China (a developing country) as an example, chooses power (maximum speed, cruising range, energy consumption per 100 kilometers), economic (acquisition costs, cost of use) and Eco-friendliness (health toxic potential, acid potential, photochemical ozone creation potential, global warming potential) indicators of different powertrain vehicles, and establishes an EWM-TOPSIS-AISM comprehensive evaluation model. The combined scores of four powertrain vehicles, battery electric vehicles (BEVs), plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), and in-ternal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs), under different power production structures in China in 2025, 2030, 2050 and 2060 are calculated. The results show that, in China, after 2025, ICEVs will completely lose competitiveness with BEVs, PHEVs, and HEVs. By 2030, BEVs will be the best vehicle among those. However, the evaluation of BEVs is characterized by high dependence and low driving force. Once China's power production structure transformation is less than expected or there is a large technological innovation in the internal combustion engine power system, the comprehensive evaluation score of BEVs will also be significantly affected. The evaluation model in this paper will provide some development suggestions for developing countries that are planning for energy structure transformation and electric vehicle development.

Keywords: Electric vehicle; Energy structure; Adversarial Interpretative Structural Model (AISM); Comprehensive evaluation

*Corresponding Author: **Zikui Bian**; Email: 376752834@qq.com

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Introduction

Transportation is an important area of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions and will continue to increase as the global economy and population grow (Huang et al. 2019). In recent years, electric vehicles have attracted extensive attention from the international community because of their characteristics of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and net-zero emissions during driving and playing an obvious environmental protection role in urban space (Wu et al. 2012; Hawkins et al. 2013; Ellingsen et al. 2016; Wang et al. 2017; Xie et al. 2018). According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), in terms of climate change, electric vehicles achieved a net greenhouse gas reduction of nearly 580 Mt CO₂-eq in APS compared to using ICEVs (internal combustion engine vehicles), exceeding Canada's current energy-related CO₂ emissions (IEA 2022).

However, research has also found that electric vehicles only have zero emissions in the process of driving (Álvarez Fernández 2018), and from the perspective of the whole life cycle, their pollutants, greenhouse gas emissions, and energy consumption are transferred to the upstream power generation field. The power energy production structure of different countries is different, and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and environmental protection brought by the promotion of electric vehicles will also be different (Wei-zheng 2012; Ke et al. 2017; Lin and Tan 2017; Wang et al. 2018; Xiong et al. 2019). It is inferred that with the increase in the proportion of clean energy power generation in the national energy structure, the role of electric vehicles in reducing greenhouse gas emissions will become more and more obvious.

However, since the end of 2023, many European and American car companies (including Ford, General Motors, Volkswagen, and Tesla) have begun to slow down or even abandon the process of promoting electric vehicles, according to China's Sina News. This has overwhelmed many countries that are laying out their own energy structure transformation and electric vehicle development. According to the Paris Agreement's goal of limiting global temperature rise to below 2°C above pre-industrial levels, preferably within 1.5°C, the promotion and use of electric vehicles is undoubtedly an important tool in the transportation sector to contribute to the Paris Agreement. How to deduce the reasonable timing for the promotion of electric vehicles based on the actual situation of each country is an important issue in the promotion of electric vehicles in each country.

At present, many evaluation methods, such as AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process), BWM (Best Worst Method), TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution), and so on, are used by researchers to judge the advantages and disadvantages of different schemes (Memari et al. 2019; Liu et al. 2020; Gahlaut et al. 2024; Sun et al. 2024). However, the traditional TOPSIS evaluation model is greatly affected by subjective factors in weight allocation (Sun et al. 2023). In order to better apply the TOPSIS model, the authors introduced an objective weighting method, the Entropy Weight Method (EWM), to obtain more reasonable weights according to the data characteristics of this study, so as to improve the reliability of the evaluation results (Xi et al. 2010; Zhang et al. 2022). The authors also use the Adversarial Interpretative Structural Model (AISM), which is a model method based on the Interpretative Structural Model (ISM) and integrated into the formation of game adversarial ideas in the generative adversarial network (GAN) (Ma et al. 2023). Compared with the traditional ISM, the AISM continuously uses the game adversarial matrix by measuring the distance between positive and negative ideal points and obtains the relationship matrix according to the partial order relationship to generate the adversarial ISM-directed topology hierarchy (Liu et al. 2022). The combination of the TOPSIS model and AISM can make the ranking results of different schemes more intuitive and improve the readability and reliability of the evaluation results (Sun et al. 2023).

In recent years, many scholars have begun to use AISM-based improvement models for programmed evaluation and impact factor exploration. For example, Y. Zhang et al. (2021) used the AISM to comprehensively analyze the influencing factors of kite culture inheritance and provide a topological model for kite culture inheritance. L. Zhang et al. (2022) created a topology map of the curriculum system against hierarchy based on the DEMATEL-TAISM model, taking the

traffic major in Liao Cheng City, China, as an example. The conclusions of the study provide a reference for the curriculum construction of transport majors in colleges and universities, especially in applied colleges and universities. Bian et al. (2022) used DEMATEL-TAISM to study the influencing factors of AI multi-cloud scheduling applied talent cultivation, which provides reference suggestions for the cultivation of AI multi-cloud scheduling applied talents. Guo et al. (2023) combine the Cross Impact Analysis (CIA) method and the Damping Interpretive Structural Model (DISM) method to construct a hazard evolution model for analyzing the evolutionary process of cascading hazard scenarios during earthquakes. Xu et al. (2023) used the AISM to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the water ecological environment of the Yangtze River Economic Belt Basin in China, and the results suggest that in the future, we should pay attention to the overall water ecological security of the basin, strengthen the regulating role of the government's water ecological management, and promote the reforms of the traditional industries and the resource-based regions, so as to achieve the sustainable development of the water ecological environment.

Currently, no scholarly evaluation based on AISM for vehicles with different power sources has been identified. Therefore, this paper takes the clean transformation process of China's electricity production structure as an example and selects the dynamic, economic and environmental performance indicators of battery electric vehicles (BEVs), plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), and internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs) under the current technical background of China. An EWP-TOPSIS-AISM evaluation model has been established for a comprehensive evaluation of different power vehicles. According to the clean process of China's electricity production, the power, economy, and environmental protection of the above models in 2025, 2030, 2050, and 2060 are comprehensively evaluated. The study aims to-

- Provide a scientific and reasonable evaluation method for the change in means of transport in the transport sector.
- Provide important theoretical support for scientific and efficient policymaking in China's transport sector.
- Provide an important reference for different countries to judge the appropriate time to promote electric vehicles according to their own national conditions.

The framework diagram of this paper is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: The research framework diagram of this paper

Data acquisition and research methods

Data acquisition

In the process of electric vehicle drivetrain design, its power and energy economy are the two most important indicators in the selection of design solutions (Chen and Guo 2013). The main indicators to evaluate the power and economy of pure electric vehicles are the maximum speed, climbing ability, acceleration time, power-to-weight ratio, driving range, energy consumption per unit mileage, and power consumption per 100 kilometers (Wang and Zhen 2007; Chen 2012). How to comprehensively evaluate different design schemes or models is a very complex problem. This paper introduces environmental protection evaluation on the basis of traditional power and economic evaluation, so as to make the evaluation of different power models more comprehensive.

The authors comprehensively considered the indicators of the four types of models: BEV, PHEV, HEV, and ICEV, and finally selected the power indicators of the maximum speed, cruising range, and energy consumption per 100 kilometers. The economic indicators are the cost of vehicle acquisition and the cost of use. The environmental protection indicators are health toxic potential (HTP), acid potential (AP), photochemical ozone creation potential (POCP), and global warming potential (GWP), as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 The influencing factors of different power vehicles

Level 1 indicators	Level 2 indicators	Unit	Nature of the indicator
Power(A)	Maximum speed (A1)	km/h	+
	Cruising range (A2)	km	+
	Energy consumption per 100 kilometers (A3)	L/100km	-
Economical (B)	Acquisition costs (B1)	Yuan	-
	Cost of use (B2)	Yuan /100km	-
Eco-friendliness (C)	HTP, Health Toxic Potential (C1)		-
	AP, Acid Potential (C2)		-
	POCP, Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential (C3)		-
	GWP, Global Warming Potential (C4)		-

The authors obtained power metrics (maximum speed and range) as well as purchase cost, one of the economy’s metrics, from China's car-buying platforms, Know Your Car Di (dongchedi.com) and Autohome (autohome.com.cn). After taking into account the fluctuation of fuel and electricity prices, battery capacity, and loss of charging and discharging efficiency over the life cycle of the car, the authors built a model to calculate the cost of using each type of car (see Appendix I for details). The authors used GREET software to measure the environmental impacts of the four participating vehicles over their full life cycle and calculated the environmental friendliness index by quantifying the environmental impacts of the above vehicles as HTP, AP, POCP, and GWP in accordance with the Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control Directive issued by the European Union (Chen 2018). The authors also calculated the changes in the above vehicle environmental indicators in 2025, 2030, 2050, and 2060 based on the changes in China's energy mix (see Table 8 for details). In summary, the parameters of the power, economy, and environmental indicators of different power vehicles are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Measured data of influencing factors of different power vehicles

Year	Type	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	C1	C2	C3	C4
2025	BEV	217	688.000	1.520	177.373	2413.349	0.003	0.042	0.040	23.800
	PHEV	170	477.000	5.300	67.048	3661.300	0.002	0.023	0.034	19.762
	HEV	180	1102.273	4.910	85.940	4227.960	0.002	0.024	0.046	26.613
	ICEV	186	823.529	6.800	67.635	6530.618	0.002	0.030	0.059	37.483

2030	BEV	217	688.000	1.520	177.373	2413.349	0.002	0.037	0.034	19.547
	PHEV	170	477.000	5.300	67.048	3661.300	0.001	0.021	0.032	18.398
	HEV	180	1102.273	4.910	85.940	4227.960	0.002	0.023	0.046	26.307
	ICEV	186	823.529	6.800	67.635	6530.618	0.002	0.029	0.058	37.114
2050	BEV	217	688.000	1.520	177.373	2413.349	0.002	0.023	0.019	9.475
	PHEV	170	477.000	5.300	67.048	3661.300	0.001	0.017	0.028	15.166
	HEV	180	1102.273	4.910	85.940	4227.960	0.002	0.022	0.045	25.577
	ICEV	186	823.529	6.800	67.635	6530.618	0.002	0.028	0.057	36.244
2060	BEV	217	688.000	1.520	177.373	2413.349	0.001	0.021	0.017	7.627
	PHEV	170	477.000	5.300	67.048	3661.300	0.001	0.016	0.027	14.573
	HEV	180	1102.273	4.910	85.940	4227.960	0.002	0.022	0.044	25.443
	ICEV	186	823.529	6.800	67.635	6530.618	0.002	0.028	0.057	36.083

Methods

1. EWM

The EWM (Entropy Weight Method) is an objective weighting method which draws on the idea of information entropy, that is, the larger the amount of information, the smaller the uncertainty, and the smaller the entropy. The smaller the amount of information, the greater the uncertainty and the greater the entropy. The EWM can determine the weight of the index according to the amount of information provided by each index, and the greater the degree of dispersion, the greater the impact of the index on the comprehensive evaluation (Zhu et al. 2020). In order to avoid the role of subjective factors, the EWM is used to obtain the weights of various indicators of dynamics, economy, and environmental protection of different power vehicles. The specific steps are as follows:

(1) Construct an evaluation matrix.

If there are m schemes, and each scheme has n evaluation indicators, of which there are n_1 positive indicators (very large indicators, i.e., the larger the better indexes) and n_2 reverse indicators (very small indicators, i.e., the smaller the better indicators), then the evaluation matrix is as follows:

$$X = (x_{ij})_{m \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \cdots & x_{1,n-1} & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \cdots & x_{2,n-1} & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{m-1,1} & x_{m-1,2} & \cdots & x_{m-1,n-1} & x_{m-1,n} \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \cdots & x_{m,n-1} & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), the value of the x_{ij} is calculated or tested by formula, and the data in this paper are shown in Table 1.

(2) Treat x_{ij} as a positive one

In the evaluation matrix $(x_{ij})_{m \times n}$,

For positive indicators:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{x_j^*}, \quad x_j^* = \min x_{ij} \neq 0, 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (2)$$

For negative indicators:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{x_j^*}{x_{ij}}, \quad x_j^* = \min x_{ij} \neq 0, 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (3)$$

(3) Calculate the proportion of the j th scheme value under the i th indicator p_{ij} .

$$p_{ij} = \frac{\alpha_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{ij}}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (4)$$

(4) Calculate the entropy of the j th indicator.

$$e_j = -k \sum_{i=1}^m p_{ij} \ln p_{ij}, \quad 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (5), $k = \frac{1}{\ln m} \geq 0; e_j = 0$

(5) Determine the weights

The weights of the j th indicator are:

$$w_{sj} = \frac{1 - e_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (1 - e_j)} \tag{6}$$

2. TOPSIS

TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution) is a comprehensive evaluation method. The TOPSIS assigns weights to each evaluation object (the weights obtained by the entropy method are used in this paper) and combines the Euclidean distance method to rank each index with the best and worst solutions (Opricovic and Tzeng 2004). The basic principle of TOPSIS is that by constructing the ideal solution and the negative ideal solution of the evaluation problem, that is, constructing the virtual optimal scheme and the virtual worst scheme, the distance between each alternative scheme and the ideal solution and the negative ideal solution is compared, and the distance between the ideal solution and the negative ideal solution is used as the criterion to test the advantages and disadvantages of each evaluation scheme. The Euclidean distance is optimal if it is the closest to the ideal solution and the farthest from the negative ideal solution. The specific steps are as follows:

(1) Calculate the weight of each indicator.

According to the entropy method, the weight w_j ($1 \leq j \leq n$) of each index is calculated separately.

(2) The evaluation matrix $X = (x_{ij})_{m \times n}$ is normalized by vector normalization method to obtain the standardized matrix.

$$Y = (y_{ij})_{m \times n} \tag{7}$$

In Eq. (7), $y_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}}$.

(3) Calculate the weighted normalization matrix.

$$Z = (z_{ij})_{m \times n} = (w_j y_{ij})_{m \times n} \tag{8}$$

(4) Determine the ideal and negative ideal solutions of the evaluation scheme.

Ideal solution:

$$V^+ = \left\{ \left(\max_i z_{ij} \mid j \in J^+ \right), \left(\min_i z_{ij} \mid j \in J^- \right) \mid 1 \leq i \leq m \right\} = \{z_1^+, z_2^+ \dots z_n^+\} \tag{9}$$

Negative ideal solution:

$$V^- = \left\{ \left(\max_i z_{ij} \mid j \in J^- \right), \left(\min_i z_{ij} \mid j \in J^+ \right) \mid 1 \leq i \leq m \right\} = \{z_1^-, z_2^- \dots z_n^-\} \tag{10}$$

In Eq. (9) and (10),

J^+ — — — set of positive indicators;

J^- — — — A set of contrarian indicators.

(5) Calculate the distance to the ideal and negative ideal solutions.

Distance to the ideal solution:

$$S_i^* = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (z_{ij} - z_j^+)^2} \tag{11}$$

Distance to negative ideal solution:

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (z_{ij} - z_j^-)^2} \tag{12}$$

(6) Calculate the proximity of each scheme.

$$C_i^* = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^- + S_i^*} \tag{13}$$

(7) Sort the scheme based on proximity.

A solution with a high degree of proximity is better than a solution with a low degree of proximity.

3. AISM

The AISM (Adversarial Interpretative Structural Model) is a model based on the ISM (Interpretative Structural Model) that integrates the game adversarial ideas in the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) (Xie 2019). Compared with the traditional ISM, the AISM continuously uses the game adversarial matrix through the distance measurement of positive and negative ideal points and obtains the relationship matrix according to the partial order relationship to generate the adversarial ISM-directed topological hierarchy diagram, and the ranking results of the evaluation objects are obtained through stepwise approximation (Zhang et al. 2022). Therefore, by intersecting the two, the scientific and rational results can be increased. The basic process model is as follows:

$$O \xrightarrow{+ \text{ Objective standard samples}} D \xrightarrow{\text{ Partial order rules}} A \xrightarrow{\text{ Shrinking}} S$$

$$S \xrightarrow{\text{ Opposing hierarchical extraction rules}} \{UP|DOWN\} \xrightarrow{\text{ The intersection of topmost features}} \text{ Pareto optimal set}$$

where D is the decision matrix, which is calculated from the fit degree of each scheme calculated in TOPSIS, and the specific steps of AISM are as follows:

(1) Determine the original relationship matrix (Yang et al. 2021).

For decision matrix D, which has m columns, there are m different metric dimensions. Positive indicators are denoted as $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_m$, and negative indicators are denoted as q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m . For any two rows x, y in the decision matrix D:

The negative indicators are $d(x, p_1) \geq d(y, p_1)$ and $d(x, p_2) \geq d(y, p_2)$ and ... and $d(x, p_m) \geq d(y, p_m)$.

The positive indicators are $d(x, p_1) \leq d(y, p_1)$ and $d(x, p_2) \leq d(y, p_2)$ and ... and $d(x, p_m) \leq d(y, p_m)$.

The partial order relationship between elements x and y is denoted as: $x < y$, which means that feature y is better than element x . That is, given a partial set of partial order $(D, <)$, there is $\forall d_i, d_j \in D$, if $d_j < d_i$, note $a_{ij} = 1$; if $d_i < d_j$, note $a_{ij} = 0$.

The decision matrix D obtains the relationship matrix $A = a_{n \times n}$ through the partial order rule, which represents the pairwise comparison results between samples of different power vehicles in different index dimensions, where the original relationship matrix $A = a_{n \times n}$:

$$a_{xy} = \begin{cases} 1 & x < y \\ 0 & \text{"x" is not exactly superior to "y" or "x" is better than "y"} \end{cases}$$

(2) Calculate the adjacency multiplication matrix and reachable matrix.

$$B = A + I \tag{14}$$

$$B^k = B^{k+1} = R \tag{15}$$

Where matrix A is the original matrix, matrix B is the multiplication matrix, matrix I is the m-order Boolean square matrix with a diagonal of 1, and Eq. (15) can be obtained by multiplying B, and matrix R is the reachable matrix.

(3) Calculate the general skeleton matrix S

$$S = HS = R - (R - I)^2 - I \tag{16}$$

In Eq. (16), HS is the Haas matrix.

(4) Calculation and drawing of directed topological hierarchy diagrams (Ni and Huang 2020)

For boolean squares, there is the reachable set R, the precedent set Q, and the common set T, where $T = R \cap Q$. Taking Relationship Matrix A as an example, for its element ei :

The reachable set of ei is denoted as $R(ei)$, which is all features with a row value of 1.

The precedent set of ei is denoted $Q(ei)$, which is the corresponding column value of all features of the feature.

The common set of ei is denoted as $T(ei)$, i.e. $R(ei) \cap Q(ei)$.

UP type

The UP-type hierarchy chart is the hierarchical division of the result priority, and its extraction rule is: $T(ei) = R(ei)$. For loop-free directed graphs (DAGs), this can be manipulated with the matrix S+I, i.e., the main diagonal in the skeleton matrix is all filled with 1. As long as the reachable set is the same as the common set, the related features are extracted. Each time, the extracted features are placed on top, and the extracted features are placed in order from top to bottom.

DOWN type

The DOWN-type hierarchy chart, i.e., the hierarchy of cause priority, is extracted according to the following rules: $T(ei) = Q(ei)$.

Each time the extracted features are placed below, the extracted features are placed in order from bottom to top. The UP type and the DOWN type belong to a set of opposites; the elements in the relationship matrix are the evaluation objects, and the advantages and disadvantages (good and bad, high and low) between the evaluation objects are represented by directed line segments. The better evaluation objects are placed at the top, so the evaluation objects at the top level are Pareto optimal.

Analysis and discussion

Obtain objective weights

The authors obtained the information entropy, information utility, and objective weights of nine of the above three first-level indicators in different years, as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3 Determination of evaluation indexes of vehicles with different power by EWM

Year		A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	C1	C2	C3	C4
2025	information entropy(e)	0.641	0.724	0.676	0.79	0.771	0.854	0.79	0.776	0.778
	information utility (d)	0.359	0.276	0.324	0.21	0.229	0.146	0.21	0.224	0.222
	objective weight (%)	16.328	12.534	14.712	9.555	10.399	6.646	9.571	10.171	10.085
2030	information entropy(e)	0.641	0.724	0.676	0.79	0.771	0.85	0.774	0.77	0.774
	information utility (d)	0.359	0.276	0.324	0.21	0.229	0.15	0.226	0.23	0.226
	objective weight (%)	16.11	12.367	14.516	9.428	10.26	6.713	10.139	10.307	10.159
2050	information entropy(e)	0.641	0.724	0.676	0.79	0.771	0.856	0.76	0.737	0.747
	information utility (d)	0.359	0.276	0.324	0.21	0.229	0.144	0.24	0.263	0.253
	objective weight (%)	15.63	11.998	14.083	9.147	9.954	6.282	10.465	11.439	11.002

2060	information entropy(e)	0.641	0.724	0.676	0.79	0.771	0.853	0.775	0.731	0.742
	information utility (d)	0.359	0.276	0.324	0.21	0.229	0.147	0.225	0.269	0.258
	objective weight (%)	15.637	12.004	14.09	9.151	9.959	6.393	9.806	11.708	11.253

Obtaining the fit degree of the solution

Using the specific calculation steps of the TOPSIS method, the authors calculated the objective weights (Table 3) by entropy method and the properties of indicators of vehicles with different power, namely, positive indicators (+) and negative indicators (-) (Table 1). The positive and negative ideal solutions (Table 4) of the nine evaluation indexes of the above four power models in different years were obtained (Table 5).

Table 4 Positive and negative ideal solutions of evaluation indexes of vehicles with different power

Year	ideal solutions	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	C1	C2	C3	C4
2025	positive	0.99999	0.99999	0.99998	0.99999	0.99999	0.92795	0.99484	0.99595	0.99999
	negative	0.00000	0.00000	0.00001	0.00000	0.00000	0.07204	0.00515	0.00404	0.00000
2030	positive	0.99999	0.99999	0.99998	0.99999	0.99999	0.91347	0.99361	0.99619	0.99999
	negative	0.00000	0.00000	0.00001	0.00000	0.00000	0.08652	0.00638	0.00380	0.00000
2050	positive	0.99999	0.99999	0.99998	0.99999	0.99999	0.89710	0.99111	0.99736	0.99999
	negative	0.00000	0.00000	0.00001	0.00000	0.00000	0.10289	0.00888	0.00263	0.00000
2060	positive	0.99999	0.99999	0.99998	0.99999	0.99999	0.90060	0.99152	0.99751	0.99999
	negative	0.00000	0.00000	0.00001	0.00000	0.00000	0.09939	0.00847	0.00248	0.00000

Table 5 Ranking of fit degree of evaluation schemes of different power vehicles

Year	Type	Ideal solution distance		Composite score index	Ranking
		Positive (D+)	Negative (D-)		
2025	BEV	0.55171596	0.73850125	0.57238521	2
	PHEV	0.61119635	0.70801063	0.53669412	3
	HEV	0.47397019	0.65949456	0.58183949	1
	ICEV	0.75333843	0.45699134	0.37757589	4
2030	BEV	0.54239236	0.77459893	0.58815798	1
	PHEV	0.60711291	0.70968369	0.53894709	3
	HEV	0.48220686	0.63380443	0.56791937	2
	ICEV	0.7675018	0.42416103	0.35594047	4
2050	BEV	0.43310186	0.81332979	0.65252659	1
	PHEV	0.60654054	0.65527535	0.51931138	2
	HEV	0.55488059	0.54826407	0.49700107	3
	ICEV	0.83426436	0.3813941	0.31373458	4
2060	BEV	0.40614812	0.83037241	0.67153953	1
	PHEV	0.60963616	0.64554476	0.51430415	2

HEV	0.56472934	0.54179398	0.4896363	3
ICEV	0.83462734	0.38148669	0.31369319	4

Adversarial directed topological hierarchy diagram

The authors have obtained the original AISM relationship matrix A, as shown in Table 9, based on the order of evaluation schemes for different power vehicles calculated in Table 5. According to the specific calculation steps of the AISM, the authors obtain an adjacent multiplicative matrix B (Table 10), thereby obtaining a reachable matrix R (Table 11), a pinched point matrix R' (Table 12), a pinched edge matrix S' (Table 13), and a general skeleton matrix S (Table 14) representing the loop in a minimalist Daisy chain. On this basis, according to the hierarchical extraction rules of UP type and DOWN type (see Table 15 for details), the obtained hierarchical extraction results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6 AISM hierarchy extraction results

Hierarchy	2025 year		2030 year		2050/2060 year	
	UP type	DOWN type	UP type	DOWN type	UP type	DOWN type
Level 0	HEV	HEV	BEV	BEV	BEV	BEV
Level 1	BEV	BEV	HEV	HEV	PHEV	PHEV
Level 2	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	HEV	HEV
Level 3	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV

Based on the AISM hierarchy extraction process in Table 15 and the hierarchy extraction results in Table 6, the authors have drawn the opposition hierarchy topology of different powered vehicles for 2025, 2030, 2050, and 2060 (Figure 2).

As can be seen from Figure 2:

First, the topological hierarchy diagram generated in this study is highly scientific and reasonable. The AISM model operation has reduced the dimensionality of the static evaluation results, making the quality of different dynamic vehicle samples clearer. After comparing the UP and DOWN oriented topological hierarchy diagrams, we can see that the main line object and arrow direction are basically the same, and the hierarchy is also basically the same, showing the hierarchical structure of 4 levels in a visual form. The directed topological hierarchy graph obtained by result priority and cause priority level extraction may be inconsistent. The intersection of the two can increase the scientific and rationality of the result. As shown in Figure 2, the positions of BEVs, PHEVs, HEVs, and ICEVs do not change in the four years 2025, 2030, 2050, and 2060, regardless of the result first-oriented topological hierarchy diagram (UP) or cause first-oriented topological hierarchy diagram (DOWN). Therefore, the topological hierarchy diagram generated in this study is highly scientific and reasonable.

Secondly, according to the principle that the higher the layer, the better the performance, and the lower the layer, the worse the performance, in the AISM topology hierarchy diagram, it can be seen that the combined ratings of power, economy, and environmental friendliness of different power vehicles are decreasing from the top to the bottom. Among them, BEVs and PHEVs will outperform HEVs in 2030 and 2050, respectively, and BEVs will always be in the top tier after 2030. Thus, the development of battery electric vehicles (BEVs) after 2030 has obvious benefits in reducing energy consumption and pollutant emissions as China's electricity production structure continues to be transformed into a cleaner one. In addition, ICEVs have been at the bottom of the list for all four years, which shows that under China's post-2025 electricity production structure, ICEVs have significantly lagged behind the other three powertrains in terms of their overall scores in terms of power, economy, and environmental friendliness.

Fig. 2: Adversarial hierarchy topology

Thirdly, the advantages and disadvantages of the comprehensive evaluation of different power vehicles are jointly determined by each sub-indicator. This time, nine secondary indicators under the three primary indicators of power, economy and environmental friendliness are selected, of which only range and maximum speed are positive indicators, and the existing technology is kept unchanged under different years, and only the change of pollutant emissions with China's electric power production structure is considered. As China's electricity production structure becomes cleaner, the environmental attributes of BEVs and PHEVs become more obvious, and as battery technology continues to advance in the future, the positive indicator of range for BEVs and PHEVs will also increase significantly. Therefore, in China's national conditions, the development of electric vehicles is undoubtedly a major direction for the transformation of the automotive industry.

Fourth, different countries should judge whether to choose electric vehicles according to their own national conditions. In this paper, for example, in China, the advantage of ICEVs over EVs no longer exists in most regions from 2025

onwards. However, this is only possible if China's installed capacity of clean energy power generation reaches 57.5% by 2025. In addition, different countries should also consider the cost of fuel or electricity for their vehicle owners and different weather conditions, etc., to adjust their transport development strategies in time so that electric vehicles can become an important tool to support the development of the national transport sector based on their own national conditions.

MICMAC analysis

The Cross-Impact Matrix Multiplication Applied to Classification (MICMAC) methodologies are mainly used to analyze the influence and dependence relationship between factors in the system. The results can be represented by coordinate axes, among which the dependence is represented by the horizontal coordinate and the driving force is represented by the vertical coordinate (Wang and Zhang 2019). The driving force of factors can be obtained by calculating the number of influencing factors of matrix element 1 in the row i of influencing factor F_i in the reachable matrix R (Table 11), that is, the driving force $D_i = \sum f_i$. The dependence of factors can be obtained by calculating the number of influencing factors whose matrix element is 1 in the column i of influencing factor F_i in the reachable matrix R (Table 11), that is, the dependence $R_j = \sum f_j$ (Wan et al. 2022). The greater the driving force, the greater the influence of the index change of this scheme on other schemes. The greater the dependence, the greater the dependence of the index change of this scheme on other schemes. The statistical results of driving force and dependence are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Driving force and dependence values of vehicles with different power

Year	Type	Driving force	Dependency
2025	BEV	2	3
	PHEV	3	2
	HEV	1	4
	ICEV	4	1
2030	BEV	1	4
	PHEV	3	2
	HEV	2	3
	ICEV	4	1
2050	BEV	1	4
	PHEV	2	3
	HEV	3	2
	ICEV	4	1
2060	BEV	1	4
	PHEV	2	3
	HEV	3	2
	ICEV	4	1

According to the size of driving force and dependence, the evaluation scheme was divided into four clusters, namely linkage group (quadrant I), independent group (quadrant II), spontaneous group (quadrant III), and dependent group (quadrant IV), and the "driving force and dependency" classification diagram of vehicles with different power was drawn, as shown in Figure 3. And-

- Correlation group (Quadrant I): It has the characteristics of high driving force and high dependence, indicating that there are correlation group factors belonging to the fuzzy correlation concept among these factors.
- Independent group (Quadrant II): It has the characteristics of high driving force and low dependence, indicating that once these elements change, other elements will also change correspondingly.
- Spontaneous group (Quadrant III): It has the characteristics of low driving force and low dependence, indicating

that these elements play the role of mediation and correlation, which is constrained by the lower level and has an influence on the upper level.

- Dependency group (Quadrant IV): It has the characteristics of low driving force and high dependence, indicating that these factors are easy to change according to other factors.

Fig. 3: Influence factors "driving force - dependence" classification

Analysis of the "driving force and dependence" classification results of vehicles with different power in Figure 3 shows that:

First, there is a strong independence between the different power vehicle evaluation scenarios. As can be seen from Figure 3, BEV, PHEV, HEV, and ICEV do not fall into Quadrant I (linkage cluster) and Quadrant III (spontaneous cluster) in the context of China's electric power production in the years 2025, 2030, 2050, and 2060 (all other things remain unchanged), and based on the characteristics of high driving force and high dependence in Quadrant I and low driving force and low dependence in Quadrant III, it can be seen that this study There is a strong independence between the different power vehicle evaluation schemes, and there are no linkage group factors belonging to the concept of fuzzy correlation. There are also spontaneous group factors that play the role of mediation and correlation. This also confirms the same phenomenon of UP-type and DOWN-type topological hierarchical maps.

Second, the ICEV evaluation scenarios are more independent. As can be seen from Figure 3, the ICEV evaluation scheme is always in Quadrant II in the context of China's power production in 2025, 2030, 2050, and 2060 (all other things being equal), and based on the characteristics of Quadrant II, which are high driving force and low dependence, it can be deduced that the independence of the ICEV evaluation scheme is relatively strong. The reason for this is that four of the nine ICEV evaluation metrics are the least environmentally friendly with China's power production structure, and once the ICEV's internal combustion engine technology takes a further leap forward (e.g., the fuel efficiency of the internal combustion engine is improved, and the pollutant emissions of the internal combustion engine system are reduced, etc.), there will be a greater impact on the comprehensive performance evaluation of other power models.

Third, the positions of the four power vehicle evaluation scenarios tend to be stable under constant technical conditions. From Figure 3, it can be seen that under China's 2050 and 2060 electricity production structures (other conditions remain unchanged), the positions of the four types of power vehicle evaluation scenarios gradually become stable, with ICEVs and HEVs located in Quadrant II and PHEVs and BEVs located in Quadrant IV. This indicates that PHEVs and BEVs are susceptible to changes in the nine evaluation criteria in HEVs and ICEVs in the context of China's 2050 and 2060 power structure production, and that once the internal combustion engine technology of HEVs and ICEVs breaks through and the economic cost of use (oil price) decreases, it will significantly affect the comprehensive performance evaluation of PHEVs and BEVs.

Conclusion

According to China's stated goal of clean power production transformation, after 2025, ICEVs will completely lose their competitiveness with BEVs, PHEVs, and HEVs under a comprehensive evaluation of power, economy, and environmental protection. In addition, by 2030, BEVs will become the best model, considering power, economy and environmental protection. However, as can be seen from Figure 3, BEVs are always in the fourth quadrant, with high dependence and low driving force. Once the transformation of China's power production structure is less than expected, there are large technological innovations in the internal combustion engine power system, and there are abnormal fluctuations in oil and electricity prices, the comprehensive evaluation score of BEVs will also be significantly affected. Moreover, national development should be planned for the long term rather than just for the present. Whether different countries should continue to develop electric vehicles should not be affected by the attitude of European and American car companies but should be based on their national conditions, especially the power production structure and climate characteristics, as the main consideration. Taking the change in China's power production structure as an example, in the case of relatively small clean energy power generation, the development of electric vehicles is indeed less than expected, but when the proportion of clean energy power generation is gradually increasing in the background. The development of electric vehicles is undoubtedly an important way to achieve energy savings and emission reductions in the field of transportation.

Limitations

In this study, the authors established a model that takes into account the driving conditions of low, normal, and high temperature scenarios. These weather scenarios are simulated in the weather conditions of Shijiazhuang, which has four distinct seasons, and the weather conditions in extreme provinces, such as the northeastern provinces and the Hainan Province, should be adjusted on the basis of the parameters of the model mentioned above.

In addition, the range of BEVs and PHEVs is mainly determined by the battery capacity, and under the current technological background, the battery capacity will change with the change in ambient temperature, which means that the range of BEVs and PHEVs in the power index will be attenuated to a certain extent under the climatic conditions in different regions, which will affect the final evaluation results.

Authors contributions

Zixiang Bian: Conceptualization, Design, Data collection, Methodology, Software use, Visualization, Writing-Original draft preparation & Interpretation, Writing – review & editing. **Zikui Bian:** Data collection, Methodology, Software use, Visualization, Writing-Original draft preparation & Interpretation, Writing – review & editing. **Xunping Lei:** Methodology, Software use, Visualization, Writing-Original draft preparation & Interpretation, Writing – review & editing. **Mohammad Kamrul Hasan:** Conceptualization, Design, Data collection, Methodology, Software use, Visualization, Writing-Original draft preparation & Interpretation, Writing – review & editing. **Wei Li:** Methodology, Software use, Visualization, Writing-Original draft preparation & Interpretation, Writing – review & editing.

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Appendix

Appendix I Use of cost modelling in economic indicators

ICEV/HEV:

$$C_1 = Q_1 f_1 LP_1 + (1 + \alpha) Q_1 f_2 LP_1 \tag{1}$$

BEV:

$$C_2 = Q_2 \gamma_1 LP_2 + (1 + \beta_1) Q_2 \gamma_2 LP_2 + (1 + \beta_2) Q_2 \gamma_3 LP_2 \tag{2}$$

PHEV:

$$C_3 = \mu_1 C_1 + \mu_2 C_2 \tag{3}$$

where C_1, C_2, C_3 denote the driving costs of ICEV/HEV, BEV, PHEV respectively; Q_1, Q_2 denote the 100km fuel consumption and electricity consumption respectively; P_1, P_2 denote the (average) price of fuel and electricity respectively; f_1, f_2 represent the ratio of regular driving scenarios to air-conditioning and cooling scenarios in fuel-driven mode; $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3$ denote the percentage of conventional scenarios, air-conditioning cooling scenarios and air-conditioning heating scenarios in the electric drive mode; α denotes the percentage increase in vehicle fuel consumption per 100 km in the fuel-driven air-conditioning cooling scenario; β_1, β_2 denote the proportion of vehicle 100 km power consumption improvement in the air-conditioning cooling and heating scenarios under electric drive; μ_1, μ_2 denote the proportion of PHEVs with fuel-driven versus electric-driven; and L denotes the total vehicle life-cycle driving mileage.

Table 8 Total installed power supply and structure in China, 2025-2060

	Unit: billion kilowatt-hours							
	2025		2030		2050		2060	
	volume	ratios	volume	ratios	volume	ratios	volume	ratios
Wind Power	5.36	18.20%	8	21%	22	29.40%	25	31.20%
Solar Power	5.59	19%	10.25	27%	34.5	46.00%	38	47.50%
Hydropower	4.6	15.60%	5.54	14.60%	74	9.90%	76	9.50%
Coal Power	11	37.30%	10.5	27.50%	3	4.00%	0	0.00%
Gas Power	1.52	5.20%	1.85	4.90%	3.3	4.40%	3.2	4.00%
Nuclear Power	0.72	2.50%	1.08	2.80%	2	2.70%	25	3.10%
Biomass & Others	0.65	2.20%	0.82	2.20%	1.7	2.30%	1.8	2.20%
Hydrogen Power	0	0%	0	0%	1	1.30%	2	2.50%
Total	29.5		38		75		80	
Clean energy share	57.50%		67.50%		92%		96%	

[Data source: (chinapower.com.cn)]

Table 9 Original relation matrix A

2025	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE	2030	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE	
						V						
						V						
	BEV			1			BEV					
	PHEV	1		1			PHEV	1		1		
	HEV						HEV	1				
	ICEV	1	1	1			ICEV	1	1	1		
2050	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	2060	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	
	BEV						BEV					
	PHEV	1					PHEV	1				
	HEV	1	1				HEV	1	1			
	ICEV	1	1	1			ICEV	1	1	1		

Table 10 Adjacent multiplication matrix B

2025	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE	2030	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE
					V						V
	BEV	1		1			BEV	1			
	PHEV	1	1	1			PHEV	1	1	1	
	HEV			1			HEV	1		1	
	ICEV	1	1	1	1		ICEV	1	1	1	1
2050	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	2060	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV
	BEV	1					BEV	1			
	PHEV	1	1				PHEV	1	1		
	HEV	1	1	1			HEV	1	1	1	
	ICEV	1	1	1	1		ICEV	1	1	1	1

Table 11 Reachable matrix R

2025	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE	2030	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE
					V						V
	BEV	1		1			BEV	1			
	PHEV	1	1	1			PHEV	1	1	1	
	HEV			1			HEV	1		1	
	ICEV	1	1	1	1		ICEV	1	1	1	1
2050	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	2060	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV
	BEV	1					BEV	1			
	PHEV	1	1				PHEV	1	1		
	HEV	1	1	1			HEV	1	1	1	
	ICEV	1	1	1	1		ICEV	1	1	1	1

Table 12 Shrinkage Matrix R 'of reachable matrices

2025	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE	2030	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE
					V						V
	BEV	1		1			BEV	1			
	PHEV	1	1	1			PHEV	1	1	1	
	HEV			1			HEV	1		1	
	ICEV	1	1	1	1		ICEV	1	1	1	1
2050	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	2060	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV
	BEV	1					BEV	1			
	PHEV	1	1				PHEV	1	1		
	HEV	1	1	1			HEV	1	1	1	
	ICEV	1	1	1	1		ICEV	1	1	1	1

Table 13 Indent matrix S 'of Indent Matrix R'

2025	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE	2030	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICE
					V						V
	BEV			1			BEV				
	PHEV	1					PHEV			1	
	HEV						HEV	1			
	ICEV		1				ICEV		1		
2050	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	2060	M4×4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV

Table 14 General skeleton matrix S

		BEV						BEV			
		PHEV	1					PHEV	1		
		HEV		1				HEV		1	
		ICEV			1			ICEV			1
2025	M4x4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	2030	M4x4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV
					V						V
		BEV			1			BEV			
		PHEV	1					PHEV		1	
		HEV						HEV	1		
		ICEV		1				ICEV		1	
2050	M4x4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV	2060	M4x4	BEV	PHEV	HEV	ICEV
		BEV						BEV			
		PHEV	1					PHEV	1		
		HEV		1				HEV		1	
		ICEV			1			ICEV			1

Table 15 Hierarchical extraction process

2025 year					
Result first - UP type extraction process			Cause Priority-Down extraction process		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
BEV	BEV, HEV	BEV	BEV	BEV, PHEV, ICEV	BEV
PHEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV, ICEV	PHEV
HEV	HEV	HEV	HEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV, ICEV	HEV
ICEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV, ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV
Remove the HEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the ICEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
BEV	BEV	BEV	BEV	BEV, PHEV	BEV
PHEV	BEV, PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV
ICEV	BEV, PHEV, ICEV	ICEV	HEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV	HEV
Remove the BEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the PHEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	BEV	BEV	BEV
ICEV	PHEV, ICEV	ICEV	HEV	BEV, HEV	HEV
Remove the PHEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the BEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	HEV	HEV	HEV
Remove the ICEV and place the upper layer.			Remove the HEV and place the lower layer.		
OVER					
2030 year					
Result first - UP type extraction process			Cause Priority-Down extraction process		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>

BEV	BEV	BEV	BEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV, ICEV	BEV
PHEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV, ICEV	PHEV
HEV	BEV, HEV	HEV	HEV	PHEV, HEV, ICEV	HEV
ICEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV, ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV
Remove the BEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the ICEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
PHEV	PHEV, HEV	PHEV	BEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV	BEV
HEV	HEV	HEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV
ICEV	PHEV, HEV, ICEV	ICEV	HEV	PHEV, HEV	HEV
Remove the HEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the PHEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	BEV	BEV, HEV	BEV
ICEV	PHEV, ICEV	ICEV	HEV	HEV	HEV
Remove the PHEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the HEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	BEV	BEV	BEV
Remove the ICEV and place the upper layer.			Remove the BEV and place the lower layer.		

OVER

2050/2060 year

Result first - UP type extraction process			Cause Priority-Down extraction process		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
BEV	BEV	BEV	BEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV, ICEV	BEV
PHEV	BEV, PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV, HEV, ICEV	PHEV
HEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV	HEV	HEV	HEV, ICEV	HEV
ICEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV, ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	ICEV
Remove the BEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the ICEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
PHEV	PHEV	PHEV	BEV	BEV, PHEV, HEV	BEV
HEV	PHEV, HEV	HEV	PHEV	PHEV, HEV	PHEV
ICEV	PHEV, HEV, ICEV	ICEV	HEV	HEV	HEV
Remove the PHEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the HEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
HEV	HEV	HEV	BEV	BEV, HEV	BEV
ICEV	HEV, ICEV	ICEV	PHEV	PHEV	PHEV
Remove the HEV and place the upper layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:			Remove the PHEV and place the lower layer. The remaining situation after removal is as follows:		
	<i>Re</i>	<i>Te</i>		<i>Qe</i>	<i>Te</i>
ICEV	ICEV	ICEV	BEV	BEV	BEV
Remove the ICEV and place the upper layer.			Remove the BEV and place the lower layer.		

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